

Rheumatic Carditis in Children Aged 3 to 15 in the Pediatric Services of the Zinder National Hospital: Epidemiological, Clinical, Paraclinical, Therapeutic and Evolutionary Aspects

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Abstract:

Introduction. Rheumatic carditis (RC) is the set of acute manifestations of heart damage during acute joint rheumatism (RAA). It is one of the most common cardiovascular diseases in children and young adults and is a major public health problem in developing countries. The purpose of our study was to describe the epidemiological, clinical, paraclinical, therapeutic and evolutionary aspects of CR in the pediatric departments of the Zinder National Hospital (HNZ).

Patients and method. It was a cross-sectional descriptive study with retro-prospective data collection spread over a period of 4 years. It concerned All children aged 3 to 15 years admitted during the study period to the pediatric departments of the HNZ, suffering from the RAA retained on the modified Jones criteria (2015) and on cardiac echocardiography data. Treatment and analysis data were made using Word, Excel and Epi Info 7.2.5.0.

Results. Our sample consisted of 39 cases of rheumatic heart disease out of a total of 31,951 hospitalized patients, a hospital

prevalence of 0.12%. The average annual prevalence was 7.8 cases with two peaks observed in 2021 (13 cases) and 2022 (20 cases). The average age of patients was 9.05 ± 3.3 with extremes of 3 and 15 years. The sex ratio was 1.1 in favor of male patients. The majority of the children (54%) came from rural areas and 61% of the parents of the respondents were not in school. More than half (52%) of our patients' parents had a low socio-economic level. The principal reasons for consultation were dyspnea (64.1%), edema of the lower limbs (10.2%), palpitations (5.1%), cough (41%) and fever (53.8%). The notion of repeated angina was found in 76% of cases. On the paraclinical level, the elevation of the CRP was observed in 72% of cases, the ASLO rate was positive in 82% of cases. Most patients (78%) had cardiomegaly. The Mitral insufficiency (MI) was the most found valve lesion (46.41%). Diuretics (87%), oxygen therapy (41%), antibiotic therapy (100%), hygienic-dietary measures (100%) were the most widely used therapeutic means. The evolution was marked by clinical stabilization in 76% of patients and survey deaths in 23.07% of cases.

Conclusion. Rheumatic heart disease exists in the Zinder region. Late consultations worsen the prognosis of these patients in whom the surgical indication comes up against a limited technical platform, hence the interest of setting up an effective prevention program against acute joint rheumatism through the correct management of throat angina.

Keywords: *Rheumatic carditis, Zinder National Hospital.*

Introduction

Rheumatic carditis (RC) is the set of acute manifestations of heart damage during acute joint rheumatism (RAA). It is one of the most common cardiovascular diseases in children and young adults. It is a major public health problem in developing countries (Maiga, 2012). Classically, RC usually occurs in children over

two years of age and adolescents, rarely in adults (Khalid, & Samy, 2015). Acute joint rheumatism affects the child from 5 years old with a frequency peak between 5 and 15 years old and even the young adult with a peak around 20 years old (Sekkali, El Ouali, & Akoudad, 2010). RAA occurs on average 20 days after group A beta-hemolytic streptococcal angina, one of the definitive sequelae of which is heart damage. The

latter can lead to death or disability for life (WHO, 2018). The annual incidence of this condition in the world's population is around 500,000 cases. The annual mortality rate secondary to RAA and rheumatic heart disease is about 350.000 (Shantinulu, Hagenebukhman, & Kwanmd, 2017). In Africa, the high prevalence of rheumatic heart disease in the school population is a public health problem as proven by some work done in children aged 5 to 16, especially in Ethiopia, Kenya, In Mali, with respective prevalences of 4.6; 2.4; 3.4 ‰ (WHO, 2017). In Niger, rheumatic heart disease accounts for 54% of cases of all acquired heart diseases with a prevalence of 1.23% of all cardiovascular pathologies in schools (Yousrah, 2014; Fa-Izou, 2022). During the year 2018, we Have seen the increase in a significant number of cases of acquired heart disease in the suspected rheumatic pediatric population. The lack of data on this subject in our context a moti. This study aims to describe the epidemiological, clinical, paraclinical, therapeutic and evolutionary aspects of rheumatic carditis in a pediatric setting at the Zinder National Hospital.

Patients and Method

It was about a descriptive cross-sectional study to collect retro-prospective data.

We included in this study, children aged 3 to 15 with RAA retained on the basis of modified Jones criteria (2015) Followed in Pediatric services A and B.

Were not included in this study, all patient records whose patient data were unusable.

The sampling was non-random, exhaustive concerning all children Aged 3 to 15 years admitted for rheumatic heart disease in pediatric departments during the study period.

Detry of the records and clinical records of patients with rheumatic heart disease.

Data Collected

The variables studied: Age, sex, parents' profession, provenance, socio-economic level, parents' level of education, reasons for

hospitalization, physical signs on admission, x-ray results, results of echocardiography, the therapeutic means used as well as the evolutionary elements.

Statistical Analysis

The data was processed and analyzed using Epi Info 7.2.5.0 and Excel software.

A value of P=0.05 had been considered significant for all tests.

Results

Epidemiological and Socio-Demographic Data

During the period of this study (4 years), out of a total of 31951 patients admitted to the servicesS of pediatrics A and B, we had recorded 39 cases of rheumatic heart disease for a hospital prevalence of 0.12%.

The average age of patients was 9.05 years $\pm$ 3.30 with extremes of 3 to 15 years.

The age group of 6 to 10 years was the most represented.

The male sex was predominant (sex ratio of 1.1) or 51% of male subjects

More than half of the patients came from rural areas or 54% of patients.

The socio-economic level was considered low to medium in 100% of cases.

More than half of the parents were not educated, or 61%.

Clinical Data

Distribution of cases of rheumatic heart disease in the child according to clinical manifestations.

Table 1. Distribution of Patients According to Clinical Manifestations

Clinical characteristics		Staff	%
Personal background	Hospitalization	25	64
	Angina	30	76
	RAA	7	17
	Other	2	5
	Dyspnoea	25	64.1

Reasons for consultation	Fever	21	53.8
	OMI	4	10.2
	Palpitations	2	5,1
General signs	Fever	21	53
	Asthenia	20	51
	Anorexia	17	43
	Weight loss	10	25
	Edema	12	30
Functional signs	Paleness	8	20
	Dyspnoea	25	64.10
	Chest pain	14	35.89
	Cough	16	41.02
	Arthralgia	10	25.64
Respiratory distress	8	20.51	

The notion of angina was found in the majority of cases (76%). The most frequent reason for consultation was dyspnea (64%). The most found general signs were fever (53%) and asthenia (51%) respectively. Dyspnea was found in more than half of the patients (64.10%).

Distribution of patients according to physical signs.

Table 2. Distribution of Patients According to Physical Signs

Variables/Physical Signs	Workforce (n)	%
Respiratory distress	8	20.51
Marginalized erythema	0	0
Subcutaneous nodule	0	0
SPM	2	5.12
HPM	3	7.69
Heart murmur	8	20.51
ICG	20	51.28
ICD	4	10,25
IC Global	15	38.46

Figure1. Distribution of Cases According to the Year of Diagnosis

Left heart failure was found in 51% (n=20) of patients.

Patients diagnosed and N 2022 accounted for 51% of cases (n=20). The average annual prevalence was 7.8 cases, with two peaks observed in 2021 (13 cases) and 2022 (20 cases).

Paraclinical Data

Distribution of patients according to the result of biology.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents According to Echocardiographic Diagnosis

Paraclinic variables	Effective (n)	%	
	Normal	15	38
Anti-streptolysin O antibody level	Elevated	32	82
	Normal	7	18
C-reactive protein	Elevated	28	72
	Normal	11	28
Hyperleukocytosis	Yes	21	54
	No	18	46

Eighty-two percent (82%) of patients had a tAuX of high anti-streptolysin O antibodies. C-reactive protein was elevated in 72% of cases (n=28).

Cardiomegaly was found in 89% of patients.

Distribution of respondents according to echocardiographic diagnosis

Table 4. Distribution of Patients Depending on the Result of Biology

Valve damage	Effective (n)	Percentage (%)
IM pure	19	48.71
IM+IAo	10	25
IM+IAo+IT	1	2,5
Endocarditis	1	2,5
IM+AM	1	2,5
IM+AP	1	2,5
IM+AM+AP	1	2,5
AM	2	5.12
AP	2	5.12
Total	39	100.00

Note: AM: myocardial involvement, AP: Pericardial involvement, AT: Tricuspid involvement, IAO: Aortic insufficiency, IM: Mitral insufficiency.

Pure Mitral insufficiency was the main anomaly found in echocardiography (48.71%).

Therapeutic Data

Table 5. Distribution of patients according to the therapeutic means used

Therapeutic variables		Effective (n)	Percentage (%)
Medical	Rest	39	100
	MHD	39	100
	Peni v	39	100
	Diuretic	34	87
	Oxygen	16	41
	Corticoids	7	17
	Iron	6	15
	IEC	4	10
Indication of surgery	Yes	26	66.66
	No	13	33.33

All patients had benefited from rest, hygienic-dietary measures and antibiotic therapy. Diuretics and oxygen therapy had been administered respectively Lying in 87% (n=34) and 41% (n=17) of cases. Surgical treatment was indicated in 66% (n=26) of our patients.

Scalar Data

Heart failure was the most common progressive complication in 100% of cases. The deaths were recorded in 23.07% (n=9) of cases.

Sixty-seven percent (67%) of the deceased patients came from the urban environment.

Diuretics were used in 97% of surviving patients (n=29). The improvement of the prognosis vital was significantly associated with the use of diuretics (P=0.01).

Discussions

In this study, the hospital prevalence of rheumatic carditis in children was 0.12%. This result is lower than those of Fa-Izou M at Niger

in 2022, Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 and Kinda G et al who reported a hospital prevalence of 0.8%, 0.3% and 0.24% respectively (Yousrah, 2014; Fa-Izou, 2022; Marie, 2002). This can be explained by the fact that their studies related not only ment to rheumatic carditis but chronic rheumatic heart disease.

The male sex was slightly predominant in our study (51%). This predominance was also reported by Baptiste J et al. in Burkina Faso in 2016 with C 54% of male patients. However, other authors such as Maiga, (2012) in Mali, Anurg, et al. (2016) in Uganda in 2015.

Andrea, et al., (2015) in Brazil in and Sara, et al., (2020) in Nigeria had reported a predominance of the female sex.

The age group of 6 to 10 years was the most represented with 43% of cases, the average age of patients was $9,05 \pm 3.3$ years with extremes of 3 and 15 years. This observation was made by other authors Aliou A in Senegal in 2015 and Kinda G et al in 2018 in Burkina had reported 9.7 ± 3.3 and 9.8 ± 2.9 years (Marie, 2002; Barakat, et al., 2018). This result could be explained By the fact that streptococcal infections occur mainly at this age.

Most (52%) of our patients came from a family with a low socio-economic level. This observation was made by Fa-Izou M. in Niger in 2022 with a rate of 54% (Fa-Izou, 2022). The low socio-economic level of patients could be associated with the occurrence of RAA and/or rheumatic heart disease probably in relation to promiscuity and poor hygiene conditions and the limitation of access to care. The almost total absence of this affection in developed countries reinforces this assertion (Scott, et al., 2023).

61% of parents had a non-school level of education. Some African authors had reported a lower percentage with 50 and 25.9% (Fa-Izou, 2022; Bruno, et al., 2016). This result could be explained by the fact that in Niger more than half of the resident population aged 15 and over has no level of education (Mohamed, 2019) with an illiteracy rate of 41.71%.

Repeated angina was the most found personal history in this study (76%). This result is higher than those reported in some Zongo series in Mali in 2019 and Njimah in Cameroon in 2020 (Njimah, et al., 2020) which were 65.8% and 66.67%.

Dyspnea was the main functional sign (64.10%). These results are almost similar to those of Fa-Izou M. in Niger in 2022 and Kinda et al in 2018 in Burkina qHe reported 73.1 and 93.5% respectively (Fa-Izou, 2022; Kone, 2014). This high frequency of dyspnea found in our series could be explained by the delay in consultation characterizing our populations. The latter consult at the stage of complication whose dyspnea is a mode of expression.

The ASLO rate was high in 82.05% cases in our study. This result corroborates with that of Kramoh in Ivory Coast in 2012 (Mohamed, 2019) who found 90.5%. On the other hand, from aOther studies carried out by Salma in Mali in 2012, and Kinda G et al in 2018 in Burkina found 26.5% and 58.33% respectively (Maiga, 2012; Sara, et al., 2020). This could be explained by the fact that streptococcal infection is very commonE in developing countries favored by promiscuity, poor hygiene conditions and the low socio-economic level of most inhabitants.

A PCR was high in 71.79% of patients. OurResult is close to those of Fa-Izou in Niger in 2022 and Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 (Richard, et al., 2019) who had reported a rate of 77% and 76.5% of cases respectively. Kramoh in Ivory Coast in 2012 And Kinda G et al in 2018 in Burkina had reported a higher percentage 80.2% and 85.7% (Marie, 2002; Mohamed, 2019). The elevation of this marker of inflammation even if it is not specific could reflect a progressive RAA or CR.

Cardiomegaly was present in 89% of our patients. She has also been found in other studies. Thus Salma M. in Mali in 2012 (Maiga, 2012) and Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 (Richard, et al., 2019) recovered 86.3% and 84.3% respectively.

Pure mitral insufficiency ranked first among rheumatic heart disease with a rate of 46.41%.

This observation was similar to those of Salma (Maiga, 2012) and Anurag in India in 2016 (Anurg, et al., 2016) who had carried by 43.5% and 48.7% respectively.

To eradicate streptococcal infection, prevent relapses and osleric transplantation, antibiotic therapy has been administered to all patients in our series (100%). All (100%) of patients inThe series directed by Fa-Izou (2022) In Niger, had benefited from antibiotics. As for Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 (Andrea, et al., 2015) had reported the use of antibiotics in 78.4% of cases.

Despite the presence of an inflammatory syndrome marking the evolution of RAA, only 17% of patients received corticosteroid therapy. Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 reported the higher administration of corticosteroid therapy (72.5%). Fa-Izou (2022) in Niger had reported less use of corticosteroid therapy (8%).

To fight against congestive heart failure, most of the treatment was based on diuretics. The latter have been administered Very in 87% of cases in our study. Richard A et al in Ivory Coast in 2019 had reported the administration of diuretics in 74.5% of cases. This therapy has stabilized 76% of patients in our series. Kinda G et al in Burkina in 2018 (Marie, 2002) Had reported clinical stability in 87.1% of cases. The use of diuretics has improved the vital prognosis of our patients ($p=0.01$).

The repair of valve lesions is based on surgery. The latter is indicated for patients aged at least 10 years with NYHA grade 3 dyspnea resistant to digitalo-diuretic treatment and a degradation of VG function with a 30% systolic ejection fraction. It is personalized for some patients. In this series we counted 26 patients for a rate of 66.66%. Kinda G et al in 2018 in Burkina Faso, Salma M in Mali in 2012 had reported a surgical indication of 61% and 84.4% respectively (Maiga, 2012; Marie, 2002). In Niger the limit of The technical platform for the realization of this gesture explains why our patients are under scheduled for surgery. In our context, this surgery is made possible thanks to the help of non-governmental organizations.

The evolution of patients was marked by the occurrence of heart failure in 100% of cases, followed by rhythm disorders in 53% and by the death of patients in 23.07%. Salma M. in Mali (Maiga, 2012). In 2012 had brought progressive complications to types of heart failure, rhythm disorder and death respectively with proportions of 60.8% and 11.7% and 4.2%.

Conclusion

Rheumatic carditis despite its low frequency (0.12%) remains a reality in the Zinder region. The delay in consultation explains the severity of the signs at the time of the consultations. The treatment is mainly medical but can in some cases call for surgery. The latter being little accessPossible because of the poverty of the population and the insufficiency of the technical platform of Care in Niger. Pending the improvement of these medico-social conditions, the implementation. In place of a program of Effective and sustainable prevention against RAA is essential in our regions. For more conclusive results, a larger study, particularly national, multicenter and prospective, is necessary.

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